

The Influence of Shopaholic Behavior, Content Marketing, and Self Reward on Impulse Buying in E-Commerce users Among Millennial Consumers in Indonesia

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study is to investigate how competency Technology in marketing activities is increasingly developing so that it has introduced e-commerce which can provide great convenience for consumers to be able to buy the goods they want anytime and anywhere. This research aims to examine the influence of Shopaholic Behavior, Content Marketing and Self Reward on Impulse Buying in e-commerce among Millennial Consumers in Indonesia. This type of research is quantitative research with an associative-causal approach. The population in this research is the Indonesian people, especially the Millennial Generation, who actively shop online on e-commerce, an unknown number. The number of samples in this research was 120 respondents. The sampling technique in this research used purposive sampling. Data analysis in this research used a Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach based on partial Least Square (PLS) using SMART PLS 4.0 software. The results prove that shopaholic behavior, content marketing and self-reward have a positive and significant effect on impulse buying on e-commerce among Millennial consumers in Indonesia.

Keywords:- Shopaholic Behavior, Content Marketing, Self Reward, Impulse Buying, E-Commerce, Millennial Consumers

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology in marketing activities is increasingly developing so it has introduced e-commerce which can provide great convenience for consumers to be able to buy the goods they want anytime and anywhere. E-commerce presents the market with the option to choose various applications to make it easier for consumers to shop. E-commerce makes it easier for consumers to carry out online buying and selling transactions which can be done from anywhere, consumers do not need large costs and a short time. Consumers can shop by utilizing online shopping. The increasing increase in consumer purchases in e-commerce will of course result in many consumer shopping experiences, so it does not rule out the possibility of impulsive purchases or impulse buying (Utami, 2010). Impulse buying is defined as unplanned purchasing behavior, which is characterized by suddenness,

very strong and determined, urgent to buy immediately, spontaneous when finding a product, and accompanied by feelings of joy and enthusiasm when buying goods or products (Rook, 1987).

Indonesia is the nation with the largest use of e-commerce worldwide, according to a poll done by We Are Social in April 2021. In Indonesia, e-commerce services are utilised by 88.1% of internet users. As more people use smartphones, the internet becomes more widely used, more people use debit and credit cards, and consumers become more confident when they shop online, the e-commerce market share will grow (Miranda, 2016). The Indonesian millennial population, which is becoming more creative every day, is one of the main drivers of e-commerce's growth, as is the country's strong interest in online shopping. As the first generation to grow up in the Internet era and as a global generation, millennials are characterised (Pendleton et al., 2021). This generation is generally characterized by increased use of and familiarity with the Internet, mobile devices, and social media, which is why they are sometimes called digital natives (Goldberg & Jeanne, 2020).

Most of the millennial generation also taught their parents to shop online (Putri, 2021). This can be seen from the results of KIC (Katadata Insight Center) research with data on one million users who shop in the six largest marketplaces, showing that the salaries of the millennial generation and generation Z are spent more on e-commerce. People spend around 3% to 5% of their monthly income on e-commerce shopping. The younger you are, the higher the ratio of income spent on e-commerce.

Daulay (2022), said that many factors can trigger impulse buying, including shopaholic behavior and promotions. Shopaholic behavior is a condition where behavior arises in someone who wants to continue shopping. Research conducted by Lailawati (2022) states that content marketing is vital if used to persuade consumers to make sudden purchases. Research conducted by Mukhopadhyay (2009) shows that consumers tend to value themselves or give rewards to themselves by purchasing or consuming products that pamper themselves.

Previous research has researched a lot about impulsive buying and the factors that influence impulsive buying. However, research regarding the influence of shopaholic behavior, content marketing, and self-reward on impulsive buying in the millennial generation is still very limited. Therefore, the researcher chose this title as the title of the research.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Consumer Behavior*

Consumer behavior according to Kotler and Keller (2009) is the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations choose, buy, use and goods, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and desires. Factors that influence consumer behavior include external factors consisting of cultural factors and social factors, in addition, there are internal factors consisting of personal factors and psychological factors.

➤ *Impulse Buying*

According to Rook (1987), impulsive buying is a sudden, often strong, and persistent urge to buy something immediately. Impulsive buying is a condition of rushing through purchasing activities as if pressed for time, without considering the subsequent consequences after making a purchase. According to Bhakat & Muruganatham (2013), 4 factors influence impulse buying, namely external and environmental stimuli, internal stimuli, situational and product factors, and demographic, social, and cultural factors.

➤ *Shopaholic Behavior*

A consumer lifestyle is always associated with a shopaholic nature. Modern society, especially teenagers today, can be said to be teenagers who have shopaholic characteristics. Shopaholic behavior can be interpreted as an individual who cannot control his desire to always shop for goods that are not always needed so this shopping activity can waste money, energy, and time (Brilianaza, 2022). According to Restiani (2021), many factors can influence an individual's shopaholic lifestyle, both from external and internal factors.

➤ *Content Marketing*

According to research (Andreas, 2013) content marketing refers to the use of content (text, images, audio, and video) in a larger form of marketing and includes basic marketing concepts, distribution and web search tools, social media, and digital advertising. According to Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2016), content marketing is the management of text, multimedia, audio, and video content aimed at engaging customers and prospects in meeting business objectives published through print and digital media, including web and mobile platforms, which is intended to provide various forms of presence. web, such as publisher sites, blogs, social media, and comparison sites. Apart from that, marketing content can be a lesson that provides stimulation and encouragement in the form of information from text, images, or audio which can influence consumer attitudes, the better the content displayed by a product makes customers interested in visiting the website (Puro, 2013).

➤ *Self-Reward*

Self-reward is a form of appreciation for yourself. The importance of self-reward includes respecting yourself more, meaning that you love your life, raising enthusiasm and motivation, good for mental health, keeping your thoughts positive, and relieving stress (Unilever, 2021). The right way to give self-reward is relevance (meaning, rewarding yourself must be in line with your goals and not contrary to those goals), and limit yourself, it is better to give gifts that can motivate yourself, and are easy to find (Vhalery, 2021).

➤ *The Influence of Shopaholic Behavior on Impulse Buying*

The results of Susilowati's research (2008), concluded that someone can be said to be a shopaholic if they show symptoms including liking to spend money to buy things they don't own even though these things are not always useful for them. Research (Daulay, 2022), states that shopaholic behavior has a significant influence on impulse buying. Shopaholic behavior reflects a high desire to have the goods they want, even though they don't need the charcoal. Research (Napitapulu 2020), states that e-shopaholic behavior contributes to increased impulse buying, such as shopaholic behavior specifically for women. Women's impulse buying behavior is influenced by internal factors such as hedonic habits and external factors such as mobile applications and promotions.

- *H1: Shopaholic behavior has a positive and significant effect on Impulse Buying in e-commerce.*

➤ *The Influence of Content Marketing on Impulse Buying*

Content Marketing is a strategy where marketers plan, create, and distribute content that can attract targeted audiences, and then encourage them to become customers that this will stimulate consumers which will influence their behavior (Muzaki and Rahmat, 2021). In this research, content marketing is assumed to be a medium for providing information and stimulation to consumers which can influence consumer behavior itself. Research conducted by Lailawati (2022) states that content marketing is vital if used to persuade consumers to make sudden purchases. Therefore, based on this explanation, the researcher formulated the following hypothesis.

- *H2: Content Marketing has a positive and significant effect on Impulse Buying in e-commerce.*

➤ *The Influence of Self-Reward on Impulse Buying*

According to research (Vhalery, 2021), it is stated that the forms of self-reward are varied, it can be with food, holidays, and so on. So, you will feel happy about yourself. One form of self-reward is giving appreciation by shopping. Therefore, a lifestyle will emerge that will influence consumers' desires and needs. Research conducted by Mukhopadhyay (2009) states that when refraining from impulse buying opportunities, consumers tend to reward themselves or reward themselves by purchasing or consuming products that pamper themselves, namely those that offer satisfaction in the short term. Based on this explanation, the researcher formulated the following hypothesis:

- H3: Self-reward has a positive and significant effect on impulse buying in e-commerce.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research data was collected using Google Forms, an online questionnaire application. Respondents came from diverse demographics regarding gender, age, educational background, occupation, income, and type of e-commerce used for shopping. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, and then the questionnaire was distributed to 120 respondents from the millennial generation who often shop on e-commerce. Data analysis in this study

used a variance-based structural equation test with the partial Least Square (PLS) SEM method using smart PLS 4.0 software. The choice of the PLS method in this research is based on the data characteristics of the SEM-PLS model which can test and identify with a low error rate even with a relatively small sample size.

Characteristics of respondents, this study collected responses from 120 respondents, because it uses an online questionnaire form, all questions can be mandatory so that respondents answer all questions can be mandatory so that all respondents answer all questions asked. The following characteristics of respondents varied greatly in this study:

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents

Items	Classifications	Number of People	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	63	52.5
	Woman	57	47.5
Ages	18-24 years	23	19,2
	25-30 years	73	60,8
	30-35 years	24	20
Job	Civil Servants/TNI/POLRI	10	8.3
	Private employees	52	43.3
	Student	21	17,5
	Entrepreneur	31	25,8
	Not yet employeed	4	3.3
	Freelancer	2	1.7
Income	<5.000.000	22	18.3
	5.000.000-10.000.000	46	38.3
	>10.000.000	52	43.3
Types of e-commerce visited	Bhinekka	2	1.7
	Blibli.com	4	3.3
	Bukalapak	3	2.5
	JD.ID	2	1.7
	Lazada	10	8.3
	Shopee	37	30.8
	Tiktok shop	35	29.2
	Tokopedia	27	22.5

The results of the item reliability test are presented in the table. It can be seen from the table that all indicators of this research variable have factor loading values greater than 0.70 (Hair, 2010). All items are said to be valid and used to test this research model.

The results of the discriminant validity test were carried out using the AVE value. The first condition must be met at this testing stage, and the AVE value must be greater than 0.5.

Table 2 Reability Test

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Shopaholic Behavior (X ₁)	0.945	0.953
Content marketing (X ₂)	0.910	0.927
Self reward (X ₃)	0.900	0.919
Impulse buying (Y)	0.939	0.948

IV. RESULTS

Inner model evaluation is a structural model that connects latent variables, with the aim of predicting causal relationships between variables or testing hypotheses. In this structural model, there is one dependent variable, namely: impulse buying (Y). The coefficient of determination (R²) of the dependent variable:

Table 3 The R-Square Value of the Dependent Variable

Model Structural	Dependent Variable	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square
1	Impulse buying (Y)	0,888	0,886
Classification: $Q^2 = 1 - (1 - (R_i^2))$ $= 1 - (1 - 0,888)$ $= 1 - (0,112)$ $= 0,888$			

Based on the model of the influence of shopaholic behavior, content marketing, and self-reward on impulse buying, it gives an R-square value of 0.888, which can be interpreted that the variability of the impulse buying variable can be explained by the variability of the variable shopaholic behavior, content marketing, and self-reward of 88.8 percent. while the remaining 11.2 percent is explained by other variables outside those studied.

This research uses a Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis approach to test the research hypothesis that was stated previously. Hypothesis testing can be done through t-statistic values and probability values through Bootstrapping which can be seen in the following figure:

Fig 1 Path Coefficient

Table 4 Hypothesis Test Results

Hubungan Antar Variabel	Koefisien Jalur	T Statistic	P Value	Ket
Shopaholic Behavior (X1) → Impulse buying (Y)	0,218	2,857	0,004	Significant Positive
Content marketing (X2) → Impulse buying (Y)	0,529	6,609	0,000	Significant Positive
Self reward (X3) → Impulse buying (Y)	0,261	3,658	0,000	Significant Positive

V. DISCUSSION

➤ The Influence of Shopaholic Behavior on Impulse Buying

The results of the analysis show that shopaholic behavior has a positive and significant effect on impulse buying. This means that the higher the shopaholic behavior among e-commerce users among Millennials in Indonesia, the higher the impulse buying behavior of Millennial consumers, and vice versa because the shopping behavior of the current millennial generation is that they think more about wants than needs. So, this is what causes shopaholic behavior to increase.

This research strengthens the results of previous research (Napitapulu, 2020), stating that e-shopaholic behavior contributes to increasing impulsive purchases, such as shopaholic behavior specifically for women. Women's impulse buying behavior is influenced by internal factors such as hedonic habits and external factors such as mobile applications and promotions. These results support research conducted (Gupta et al, 2022), which states that shopaholic behavior has a significant effect on impulse buying. Shopaholic behavior reflects a high desire to have the desired item.

➤ The Influence of Content Marketing on Impulse Buying

The analysis results show that content marketing has a positive and significant effect on impulse buying. This means that the more effective content marketing that Millennial consumers receive, the higher the impulse buying among e-commerce users among Millennials in Indonesia. Vice versa, because content marketing can be used to attract consumers to make purchases.

This research strengthens the results of a study conducted by Milhinos, 2015 which stated that content marketing is very vital if used to persuade consumers to make sudden purchases. This is also in line with research (Athar, 2022) which states that marketing content can be a driving force for consumers to make purchases.

➤ The Influence of Self-Reward on Impulse Buying

The results of the analysis show that self-reward has a positive and significant effect on impulse buying. This means that the higher the self-reward that e-commerce users have among Millennials, the higher the impulse buying among e-commerce consumers among Millennials in Indonesia. Vice versa, because self-reward is an appreciation for yourself by giving gifts or something similar, this self-reward trend is currently popular among millennials in Indonesia.

This research strengthens the results of a study conducted by Mukhopadhyay (2009), stating that when refraining from impulse buying opportunities, consumers tend to reward themselves or reward themselves by purchasing or consuming products that pamper them. There are various forms of self-reward, including food, holidays, and so on (Vhalery, 2021). So, you will feel happy about yourself. One form of self-reward is giving appreciation by shopping. Therefore, a lifestyle will emerge that will influence consumers' desires and needs (McMains et al, 1968).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the research analysis and the results of the discussion in the previous chapter, the conclusions of this research are as follows: (1) Shopaholic behavior has a positive and significant effect on impulse buying in e-commerce among millennial consumers in Indonesia. (2) Content marketing has a positive and significant effect on impulse buying in e-commerce among millennial consumers in Indonesia. (3) Self-reward has a positive and significant effect on impulse buying in e-commerce among millennial consumers in Indonesia.

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